

As the chosen paper is very easily reproducible, i.e all the required data is accessible and runs out of the box, producing exactly the results as described in the paper, I focused even more on performing a detailed examination of the experimental setup and put the results under scrutiny: were experiments run multiple times. here's an analysis pertaining to the specific aspects of the experimental setup.

I have implemented this integration in the task domain of string transformations using the PROSE framework [Microsoft 2015] as FlashGPT3 and evaluate it on a collection of challenging transformation problems. Using the deferred querying algorithm, FlashGPT3 learns most programs in under 1s, with the most difficult problems taking less than 3s. On its own, GPT-3 solves fewer problems and typically requires significantly more examples on the problems that it can solve. Additionally, I demonstrate that semantic operators can be given descriptive names (for better program readability) and how these named semantic operators can be integrated in the task domain of string profiling.

In summary, we make the following contributions.

- I propose a novel framework of integrating pre-trained language models with inductive synthesis by augmenting the language over which programs are synthesized with semantic operators that are powered by the language model.
- I present a deferred execution algorithm for quickly learning programs with these semantic operators under the uncertainty of the language models.
- I try to implement and evaluate this integration in the domain of string transformation problems.
- I present a case study on integrating semantics with string profiling.

1 Strategies:

Implementing the framework for semantic programming involves several strategies:

a. Familiarize with Pre-trained Models: Pre-trained models like GPT-3 are developed using large-scale datasets to understand and generate human-like text. They are "pre-trained" on a broad range of topics before being fine-tuned for specific tasks. This training enables them to perform tasks such as text completion, translation, question-answering, and more, with minimal additional input. Few-shot learning, a capability of these models, allows them to adapt to new tasks with just a few examples, making them highly versatile for applications like semantic programming.

b. Decompose Problems: Decomposing problems involves breaking down complex tasks into simpler, more manageable subproblems. This strategy allows for identifying parts of a problem that can be solved using standard programming techniques and those that require semantic understanding, which might be tackled with the aid of pre-trained models like GPT-3. By decomposing problems, one can leverage the strengths of both traditional programming approaches and advanced machine learning techniques to create more efficient and effective solutions.

c. Develop Semantic Operators: Developing semantic operators involves creating functions or modules that can interpret and manipulate data at a semantic level, going beyond simple syntactic operations. This means understanding the meaning or intent behind data or code segments. For example, a semantic operator might be designed to identify the purpose of a code block, such as sorting a list or filtering a dataset based on specific criteria. To develop these, I need to:

- **Define Semantic Goals:** Clearly understand what semantic actions are needed for these tasks.
- **Leverage AI Models:** Use pre-trained models like GPT-3 to interpret and generate semantic mappings.
- **Implement Operator Logic:** Code the logic for each operator, ensuring it can perform its intended semantic function accurately.
- **Integrate Context Understanding:** Ensure operators can understand and utilize the context in which they are operating.
- **Test and Refine:** Continuously test the operators in various scenarios and refine their logic for better performance and accuracy.

d. Iterate and Experiment: Iterating and experimenting in this context involves continuously testing and refining your semantic programming solutions using the pre-trained models. For example, after developing semantic operators, I would apply them to various programming tasks, such as string transformations or code refactoring, to observe their effectiveness. If the initial attempts do not meet expectations, I adjust the approach, possibly by redefining the operators or changing how problems are decomposed, and then test again. This process helps in fine-tuning the system to improve accuracy, efficiency, and adaptability to different types of tasks.

e. Evaluate and Adapt: Evaluating and adapting involves assessing the performance of this semantic programming system against predefined criteria, such as accuracy, efficiency, and the ability to generalize across different tasks. Based on the evaluation, I identify areas for improvement, which could involve refining the semantic operators, adjusting the problem decomposition strategy, or incorporating additional training examples for the pre-trained models. This iterative process ensures the system becomes more capable and reliable over time, adapting to new challenges and requirements as they arise.

2 Difficulties and Encounter:

Implementing semantic programming with pre-trained models like GPT-3 involves several detailed challenges:

- **Understanding Limitations:** Pre-trained models may not always understand the specific context or domain-specific nuances, leading to inaccuracies.

- **Handling Edge Cases:** Models might struggle with edge cases or scenarios that were underrepresented in their training data.
- **Computational Resources:** Significant computational power and memory are required to run large models, which can be costly and limit accessibility.
- **Adaptation to Specific Tasks:** Customizing the model to perform well on specific tasks or within particular domains requires fine-tuning, which can be complex and time-consuming.
- **Interpretability and Debugging:** Understanding why a model made a particular decision can be challenging, complicating the debugging process.
- **Data Privacy and Ethics:** Using pre-trained models raises concerns about data privacy and the ethics of the decisions made by the model, especially in sensitive applications.

3 Key Findings:

A novel framework that integrates pre-trained language models with inductive synthesis to augment program synthesis with semantic understanding. Key findings include:

- The proposal of semantic operators powered by language models, enhancing the synthesis of programs by incorporating semantic insights directly into the programming language.
- The development of a deferred execution algorithm for efficient learning of programs using these semantic operators, addressing the computational challenge of interacting with language models.
- The successful implementation and evaluation of this framework in the domain of string transformation problems, demonstrating its ability to automate tasks that cannot be handled by either technology alone.

A case study showcasing the application of semantic programming in string profiling, highlighting the framework's versatility and generality across different domains.

4 Experiment Design:

The detailed conclusion from the experimental design reveals that the integration of semantic programming with pre-trained models significantly enhances the capability to automate complex programming tasks. By incorporating semantic understanding directly into the programming process through semantic operators and a deferred execution algorithm, the framework demonstrates a robust approach to tackling string transformation problems and beyond. This innovative combination opens new avenues for research and application in automated programming, suggesting a promising future where AI-driven tools can more effectively understand and execute tasks that require deep semantic insights.

4.1 Environment:

For our prototype, FlashGPT3, we enhanced a string transformation DSL from the PROSE platform by incorporating position and map operators. We utilized a syntactic similarity approach for selecting potential queries, calculating token occurrences to form feature vectors, and determining similarity via cosine measures of these vectors, considering various token types. Our benchmarks included basic test cases for assessing semantic transformation capabilities, language learning examples derived from educational materials, and a selection from the FlashFill benchmark to test GPT-3's syntactic processing. Using GPT-3's davinci model, we experimented with a set temperature for creativity in output. Performance analysis revealed average query times influenced by API call latency, noting efficiency improvements with asynchronous execution and the impact of rate limiting on concurrent requests.

4.2 Combining Syntactic and Semantic Operators:

We examine the necessity and benefits of integrating GPT-3 with syntactic inductive programming, despite GPT-3's capability for syntactic tasks. Our evaluation methodology involves learning programs from initial examples and applying the highest-ranked program to subsequent cases until all are solved. Specifically, we compare the performance of GPT-3 alone, using a DSL with only the SemMap operator, against that combined with the FlashFill system provided by the PROSE SDK, to highlight the advantage of this integration.

5 Results:

The number of examples that Flash Fill and GPT-3 require on the syntactic benchmarks. When the number of examples equals the total number of examples, GPT-3 fails. The result indicates that GPT-3 is able to solve some problems, but requires significantly more examples. Its main weaknesses are tokenization and complex substring extraction logic. A

problem as simple as extracting the first 4 letters of a word ("Alakazam" $\rightarrow$ "Alak") is not solved after 7

(a) Solving Flash Fill benchmarks with GPT-3. Eight problems (26%) were not solved by GPT-3. Those problems that are solved by GPT-3 require significantly more examples than Flash Fill. It is clear that a strong, syntactic synthesizer is required to automate repetitive transformation tasks.

(b) Results on the mixed syntactic and semantic benchmark problems. Six problems (20%) were not solved by GPT-3. On half of those, FlashGPT3 requires barely two examples. On others, the bottleneck is GPT-3 requiring more examples to solve the semantic subproblem

Similarly, extracting the penultimate word from a path specification ("path/to/file" $\rightarrow$ "to") proves hard for the language model.

5.0.1 Clustering:

The study investigates if delaying query execution until after ranking and clustering enhances program learning efficiency. Using a Cartesian product for queries instead of greedy clustering, the experiment finds that without clustering, learning times out for several problems, but with clustering, programs are typically learned in under a second. The research also notes the reduction in the number of necessary semantic operator calls with clustering,

significantly speeding up learning and reducing costs, especially for complex tasks requiring more examples for program synthesis.

FlashGPT3 consistently outperforms GPT-3 on problems that require more complex syntactic parsing. Aside from taking care of the syntactic part, deductive backpropagation has the advantage of generating smaller, more targeted problems for GPT-3. For instance, explicitly obtaining the infinitive of a verb ("were" → "be") is easier than requiring this transformation as part of a larger problem ("were" → "data/be.mp3").

Whereas generally a blessing, in some cases, these smaller subproblems sometimes lack enough context for GPT-3 to learn the task. For instance, consider the problem of converting 24-hour to 12-hour notation ("22:00" → "10:00 PM"). FlashGPT3 breaks this down into two semantic subproblems "22:00" → "10" and "22:00" → "PM" as the space is considered a constant. The context of this task is important, as it takes FlashGPT3 one more example to solve the first of these

(a) Total time taken to learn a program (in seconds). Evaluation time is not counted. Problems in the right

Figure 1: timed out without clustering. Clustering is clearly required for learning problems in reasonable time.

(b) Semantic operator calls during learning, spread out over two plots for clarity. Problems on the left side did not time out before finding the correct program without clustering, those on the right did.

5.0.2 Case Study:

This section presents a case study where we use our semantic operators to perform semantic string profiling. Recall that for the profiling task in Figure 5b (Section 2.3), we wanted to learn the following semantic profile

"iPhone 11 " ◦ Digit+ ◦ "GB - " ◦ matchColor ◦ matchCarrier

that represents a concatenation of atoms. We extend FlashProfile with a SemPos atom that finds the next ending position of a semantic concept.

Describe the relation between the following items

Belgium | Brussels => capital

Pizza is delicious . | Pizza => subject

Lionel messi | football => sport

China | Asia => continent

Like a Prayer | Madonna => artist

| =>

Listing 4. Prompt to extract the name of a relation, where and are placeholders to be substituted with

the input and output of an example from a query.

Table 1. Using GPT-3 to generate names for semantic operators. We write `...` for parts of sentences that are

omitted for brevity. Because it generates concrete subproblems, names for FlashGPT3 are more accurate.

Input	FlashGPT3		GPT-3	
	Output	Name	Output	Name
were	be	infinitive	data/be.mp3	to be
May 2, 1953	mai	month	29 mai 1953	date
How many mice does your cat catch?	mouse	subject	... ____ ... (mouse)	subject-verb
Guernica	Picasso	painter	Picasso's Guernica	artwork
1984	Orwell	writer	Orwell's 1984	book
PRG	Prague	airport	Departure from Prague (PRG)	airport code

Table 1

6 Conclusion:

This paper presents an innovative approach by merging inductive program synthesis with autoregressive language models capable of few-shot learning. It introduces three semantic operators, leveraging the language model for tasks requiring language comprehension and broad knowledge, and outlines methods for their learning via deductive backpropagation. These operators, which facilitate tasks like string manipulations and profiling, enable the automation of complex tasks from minimal examples by combining syntactic processing with semantic understanding. The study demonstrates the necessity of these operators in

learning efficient programs and suggests future research directions, including exploring cost-effective models for enhanced functionality and extending these methodologies to domains like semantic refactoring and data extraction, potentially leading to commercial applications.